

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING ORAL SPEECH IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSONS IN AUDITORIUMS OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY FIELDS

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Annotation

This article examines typical problematic situations that arise when teaching oral speech to Uzbek students in Russian language classes. Deeply studies the process of teaching Russian oral speech to foreign students and lists the factors that negatively affect the development of the material in a non-linguistic environment. The purpose of our study is to introduce students studying in the technical field to this problem and suggest ways to solve it.

Key words: oral speech, hearing ability, information technology, educational efficiency, 3D glasses, innovative methods.

Аннотация

в данной статье рассматриваются типовые проблемные ситуации, возникающие при обучении устной речи узбекских школьников на уроках русского языка. Глубоко изучает процесс обучения русской устной речи иностранных студентов и перечисляет факторы, негативно влияющие на освоение материала в неязыковой среде. Цель нашего исследования – познакомить студентов, обучающихся в технической сфере, с этой проблемой и предложить пути ее решения.

Ключевые слова: устная речь, слух, информационные технологии, эффективность обучения, 3D-очки, инновационные методы.

Introduction

Currently, there are many problems that can be identified in teaching the Russian language to the Uzbek audience, among which the following can be noted:

includes speech and radio broadcasting. These processes are closely related to teaching a foreign language.

is not to teach individual words and phrases, but to teach understanding of the general concept: what it is about, where and when the action takes place, who are its main participants and students aimed at general understanding of the text [1].

Figure 1. Scheme of radio broadcasting during the lesson

In Uzbekistan , many students enter the Russian language department without any motivation, according to the distribution after the selection.

and well-paid job after training . Many of them do not understand how the Russian language will help them achieve this goal, whether they speak Russian in business matters, whether they need Russian for tourist trips , and why they should learn it at all [2].

Therefore, the main task of all modern professors and teachers is to arouse interest in learning the Russian language in engineering students, the goals of language learning, what perspectives and opportunities the Russian language opens for them, why this country is a good place to work. , is to talk about how interesting it is to travel.

We monitor students' interest in the Russian language during the lesson. Since students lose interest in the long learning process, "the creation of clear motivational conditions, the correct selection of tasks, content, methods, tools and forms can be considered important and influential factors in teaching the Russian language" [3].

It is important for students to develop both the general motivation of the course of learning Russian as a foreign language and for each individual lesson. Preparing e-textbooks for each specialty subject so that students understand why they do certain exercises, what skills they develop and how they can help them realize their plans in the future plays a very important role in training young technologists who think creatively, such as oil and gas chemistry. Russian language plays a very important role for students in the educational process in the industry, experience shows that the role of animated field electronic textbooks is very important for them to become mature personnel of their field in the future [4].

Part of the problem is the inadequacy of modern methods of teaching the Russian language.

In the auditorium of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, a lot of attention is paid to the study of grammar when teaching the Russian language. At the same time, students do not spend time in class to develop speech. The student studies the Russian language for several years, knows grammar well, translates the texts given by the teacher; then when he starts working in several Russian companies in Uzbekistan, he realizes that he cannot explain himself even in the simplest everyday situations. He goes to the store and does not understand how to buy the products he needs, although he knows the names of vegetables and fruits, he has studied grammar, but how they are pronounced in a real speech situation is completely incomprehensible to him . A person, for example, is more afraid of problematic situations that arise in the management of oil and gas technologies, where he can explain some of the processes taking place only with gestures [5]. And the question arises, why did he study grammar and translate texts for so many years if he could not say anything?

Let's see why this happens? What are the mistakes in teaching Russian and how to correct them?

First, the outdated grammar-translation method is used in teaching. It does not meet the goals of students learning Russian. They want to talk to real people, get to know each other on social networks. networks , communicating with Russians in Russia, knowing a living language that you understand, in which you can get basic household services, work and correspond with Russians, watch films and video clips, read modern literature.

Figure 2. scheme for watching video clips

That is, it is necessary to use the communicative method in teaching and develop students' lively communication skills, perform speech exercises for various life situations, create and develop communicative situations, and, of course, speak and listen to modern speech more. And this is a completely different curriculum, different textbooks, modern materials, use of Internet technologies, use of forums, social networks are considered very important. This is modern Russian news, video clips, weather reports, watching videos in classes. It gives students the opportunity to learn about modern Russian culture and communicate on common topics six months after the start of studying the Russian language. And this is already interesting, and it encourages me to devote more time to studying the Russian language and modern Russian culture. After a year of studying Russian, such a student will have the opportunity to compare what films and clips he watches at home with his peers in Russia, and students often do such things in their free time. They themselves tend to make friends, learn to write postcards for holidays, ask questions about work, hobbies and talk about other topics that interest this student [6].

Secondly, teaching is structured in such a way that the active role in the educational process belongs to the teacher. Students passively listen and translate what is said. With this approach, you can study a foreign language for many years, starting from school, but then you will not understand what the foreigner said to you and what he should answer in this situation. As a result, a schoolboy or student can translate the text well with a dictionary, but he cannot say anything in Russian, he does not understand what he is being asked about [7].

If the student takes an active position in the lesson, his individual interests and language learning goals are taken into account, and the teacher competently guides the student, encourages, suggests, explains what is necessary and important, learning is more effective. approach. he , he talks to him, he discusses live talk. It should also be noted that small authentic texts and audio materials can be given to students in the first months of learning the Russian language, and the volume of such materials can be gradually expanded. If the teacher only explains grammar and gives homework for translation, his students will never speak and will not fully understand Russian by ear. Because speech activity consists of such skills as reading, listening, writing and speaking. All these skills are closely related. Inadequate mastery of any of them destroys the entire learning process [8].

Foreigners to understand the Russian language as a whole system, to develop all types of speech activities at the same time, to apply their knowledge in practice and to communicate in Russian. In order to solve the specified problem, it is necessary to "choose the appropriate language material, the content of which shows the effect of this unit in

communication, taking into account the real needs and interests of students, to ensure innovation. creating favorable conditions for material and communication".

Thus, teachers should use the communicative method of teaching the Russian language instead of the outdated grammar-translation method.

of educational materials and modern textbooks. What educational materials are used in teaching the Russian language? These are such outdated texts that even every modern Russian person (native speaker) does not understand the meanings of the words used in the text. Such texts do not allow students to use words from these texts in conversation. Native speakers do not understand foreigners because they use words that were spoken more than 50 years ago and are no longer relevant today. It is very important to choose the right modern teaching materials and update all textbooks. Textbook is the main teaching tool. It is a guide in the work of teachers and students and includes samples of oral and written speech, material of language and local studies, which are selected taking into account their functional load in various forms of communication and types of speech activity, and established. to account for students' experience in their mother tongue and prevent interference [9].

What textbooks should be used? It is structured according to modern, communicative teaching methods. The information they provide is completely different. They use a step-by-step approach to learning. Currently, six levels of knowledge of the Russian language are defined and described: basic knowledge (levels A1, A2), independent competence (levels B1, B2) and fluency (levels C1, C2). All these levels correspond to the European level scale. There are certain requirements for each level of language proficiency, thanks to which each student and teacher can understand what to strive for, what goals to set and what to learn. In addition, students are encouraged to learn the language by taking an exam for the level of Russian language proficiency and receive a certificate for each of them. The effectiveness of the teacher's work can be monitored by the number of students who passed these exams. The step-by-step approach fundamentally changed the entire educational paradigm of the Russian language as a foreign language system, reconfiguring it to emphasize new parameters in the assessment of achievements. The main thing is not the acquisition of a certain amount of knowledge, but the level of formation of practical skills and abilities that can solve certain communicative tasks in real speech practice, in real situations of speech communication . Thus, "as parameters for dividing the levels, they began to consider, first of all, communicative tasks that students can solve through language, as well as the topic-content side of communication, the topics and situations in which speech activity takes place." It is important to replace existing textbooks with new ones so that students can assess the level of knowledge and teachers can monitor [10].

Modern textbooks have web applications for this. They make Russian language lessons more interesting and effective.

These can be :

- ✓ Audio texts or podcasts with comments and methodological recommendations of the teacher
- ✓ Audio textbook dialogues
- ✓ Video recordings of songs, excerpts from movies
- ✓ Learning exercises that automatically check the student's answer
- ✓ Test assignments
- ✓ Copybooks for teaching writing techniques

- ✓ Electronic dictations. with automatic writing of text
- ✓ Visual materials - pictures, photographs, maps
- ✓ Electronic dictionary for all lessons of the textbook
- ✓ To additional Internet resources, in social networks, first of all,

Multimedia technologies in teaching the Russian language

Language environment plays a big role in the learning of Russian as a foreign language by Uzbeks. "Language environment can be natural and artificial". If the student is not in the language environment, he must create another view. Modern technology can give students the opportunity to be in such a field. Technological progress does not stand still, and many students still complain about the lack of elementary things such as audio recordings, video recordings and presentations.

Figure 3. Software tutorial in 3D glasses

Also, students have a serious problem with insufficient language environment: no live communication, no Russian TV channels, no communication on social media resources, etc. Teachers should modernize and diversify their material with the help of speech and communication exercises, make presentations using audio recordings, video clips, analysis of modern films (or their fragments), explaining materials and practicing speech communication skills.

You can use the electronic communication environment to solve many problems. For example, YouTube video service, social networks. This is, firstly, a lively language, and secondly, interesting topics for students [11].

Methods of organizing electronic communication in teaching the Russian language:

1. Participation of students in an individual or group telecommunication project.
2. Maintaining online diaries, online magazines, blogs as a means of solving the problems of professional self-education of foreign students.
3. Communicating with a pen pal as a representative of the language world being studied.
4. Communicate in forums or in comments to the video

Use of e-mail, sms and messengers for interactive exchange of information between students and the teacher within the framework of educational courses.

Conclusion

Thus, there are many global problems in teaching the Russian language: lack of motivation among Uzbek students, misunderstanding of the goals of language learning, use of outdated

teaching methods, lack of qualified teachers and lack of native speakers. Interactive methods of communication in the language environment and teaching without the use of modern technical teaching tools in the classroom. All these problems should be solved comprehensively and step by step. Nowadays, there are great ways to make lessons fun and interesting, good modern textbooks. Therefore, we have created e-science content and e-textbooks for each of our subjects. We also believe that it is very important to use multimedia technologies and new textbooks with various applications created for teaching according to the communicative teaching methodology.

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